

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article highlights the importance of a number of methods and technological tools for learning foreign languages online, as well as a wide range of ways to engage young people in languages through a variety of interactive methods.

Keywords: gamification, interactive method, electronic notebooks, multimedia tools, active board, interactive device, smartphone, internet tablets.

At the time being, our equiminal is developing rapidly. It is no exaggeration to say that various changes and innovations are clearly visible in this process. In today's technological age, if we stop moving and researching for a second, everything stops for us. One second can change your whole life. If you want to find your place in the current evolving age, you must know at least three foreign languages. The only thing you can do is learning harder and harder. It is coincidence that our people say, "Who knows many language, he knows world." Learning foreign languages opens the door to the future. By this process you can find a partner in any country and start your own business. It should be noted that there are many ways to learn a foreign language. It is very important to choose this way correctly and accurately. You can master anything in anytime, anywhere by distance learning. In this form of education, only attention and competence are required from the student. In the 21st century, students have developed to such an extent that simple teaching methods have become boring for them. Every teacher who wants to involve students in the teaching process must use modern technologies during the lessons. In addition, through various interactive methods young are paid attention to the lesson. However, teaching in this and similar ways is only useful in the upper grades and sometimes in the primary grades. But if we teach English to young children at the first time, we have to use different games. Young children are usually fans of games on mobile phones. Imagine : a child opens a smartphone, opens a game based on learning foreign languages and starts playing on it. After a while, he achieved some results and won points and medals. Out of curiosity, he resumed his game, and note that at this time he will have the opportunity to acquire the knowledge imparted through the games. The process of using similar game mechanics even in non-game situations is called gamification, and the term has been used in many business communities around the world for several years. Gamification is a application of game-design elements and game principles in non-game contexts. The technology of adapting methods to non-game processes and events. Therefore, we can say that the use of modern technical means in learning a foreign language not only facilitates the acquisition of a foreign language, but also the development of business in the country. In the process of teaching a foreign language, it is intended to develop students' worldview, thinking skills, to improve their knowledge of their native language by mastering this language. Another simple way to quickly learn a foreign language is a dictionary. With this in mind, a variety of picture games have been created. Our children inadvertently memorize new words by trying to win and score points in this game. They can not only learn the word through these games, but also learn its pronunciation. Even if they do not have a specialist, they can learn the words themselves through these games. That is, these types of games are adapted not only for young children, but

also for adults. These games should also not be played for a long time, as it can cause various serious diseases in our health, especially, it may impact on our vision. So, if we talk about modern technological tools one by one, they are so many that I will now briefly describe the most common tools. Electronic notebooks (organizers) belong to the "lightest class" of computing computers (this class also includes calculators, electronic translators, etc.); they weigh no more than 200 grams. Organizers are not programmed by the user, but have a large amount of memory. It can be used to write the necessary information and use it to edit special text, texts of work letters, agreements, contracts, agendas and business meetings.

Multimedia - Provides computer-generated music and audio content. Active board (interactive whiteboard) is a modern teaching tool that works in conjunction with a computer and a projector. An interactive device is an electronic device that can be mounted on a projection board (magnetic board, marker board, class board, classroom wall) or on the projector itself and make any flat, smooth work surface interactive. Smartphone means "smart phone" in English. A mobile phone that is functionally close to a pocket PC. It has all the features of a pocket computer. Internet tablets are a special mobile device that is a classic example of a personal computer. Tablets (for example, iPad) are completely different from computers in appearance. Tablets consist only of a screen, and other peripherals (mouse, keyboard) are organized in virtual form. The tablets specialize in accessing Internet services and working with documents through a fully mobile environment. All of the above are common tools today, and teachers make extensive use of the above tools to increase the effectiveness of their teaching processes and to arouse students' interest in the teaching process. They can learn foreign languages quickly and easily, and we can develop the ability of young people to learn by listening through the multimedia tools mentioned above. Science has also proven the hypothesis that a person learns quickly by listening to certain information.

Conclusion. In addition, the online implementation of the tasks given to students not only arouses the interest of students, but also increases their intellectual potential. Students will be able to receive and send information quickly. In addition, completing tasks online will ensure that the assessment is fair to some students. We will put an end to corruption in the system. Naturally, this situation is an important factor in the development of mature and talented personnel.

References:

1. Evans V., Dooley J., Wright S. Information Technology Издательство: Express Publishing, 122p., 2011
2. A.T.Kenjabayev, M.M.Ikramov va boshq. Axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari: o'quv qo'llanma. Toshkent. 2017.
3. https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Main_Page.